

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGY OF CRAFT CANDY FOR FUNCTIONAL PURPOSES FOR RESTAURANT INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

The article describes the technology of making functional candies for restaurants. Non-traditional fruit and berry raw materials are used for production.

Keywords: candies, technology, restaurants, physalis.

Formulation of the problem. Many (several thousand) natural and artificial food products are used in the structure of modern human nutrition, and a huge number of different diets are known. But in recent years, the so-called functional products (FP) - Food for Specific Health Use - have increasingly confidently invaded this food diversity. The difference between these products and traditional ones is that they have not only nutritional properties, but also have a targeted effect on the functional activity of individual organs and systems of the body with preventive and therapeutic purposes.

Now many countries have programs to create functional food products. The first project to create functional products was developed in Japan in 1984. In 1987, about 100 functional products were created. In Japan, the direction of development of functional products has found wide government support. In 1991, the concept of "Foshu" - "Foods for Specified Health Use" - products for special health nutrition was developed in Japan. In Ukraine, the concept of creating and introducing functional health products has not yet been approved by the government, despite the fact that the problem of improving the nation's health is the most acute.

Analysis of recent research and publications.

Functional products include products that have a positive effect on human health when used regularly in effective doses. In addition to nutritional ingredients, they contain functional ingredients that have a positive effect on the human body, which helps to adapt to the effects of the external environment, prevent the occurrence of diseases and prevent premature aging [1-3].

Functional products are considered not only as a source of plastic substances and energy, but also as a complex non-medicinal complex that provides a reliable therapeutic and preventive effect. The place of functional food products is defined as intermediate between products of general use and medical food products. Functional products differ from traditional products primarily in the absence of antinutrients and a balanced amount of macro and micronutrients.

The direction of creation of therapeutic and preventive preparations and complexes from natural plant

raw materials is actively developing [4-6]. Of all the variety of known plant species, people use only those that are available and familiar to them. This situation is explained by low information about the nutritional and biological value of many types of plant raw materials, conditions of growth, storage and processing, as well as the complexity of technologies for processing raw materials and obtaining functional food products [7].

The analysis of literary sources on the research of physalid and its processing showed that the range of presented products is quite narrow and does not have a functional orientation. There are no studies in the direction of the technology of complex processing of physalis fruits into functional products [8].

Physalis belongs to the nightshade family. It is an annual or perennial herbaceous plant with a creeping rhizome, angular-curved stems 0.4 — 3 m high. The round, cherry-sized fruits of physalis, the weight of which does not exceed 5 g, are surrounded by a thin parchment-like ribbed envelope of flower leaves (a distinctive feature physalis is the presence of a film shell, which shows the fruit in the form of a cover). The structure of the physalis fruit is a berry. Its skin is thin, oily, shiny, yellow-burnt in color. The pulp of the fruit is jelly-like, transparent, light yellow or yellow-hot in color. Numerous small, soft white seeds are located in the pulp and are eaten together with it. The taste of the fruit is refreshingly sweet, sweet-sour or sweet-tart, reminiscent of pineapple and passion fruit. Physalis is used fresh as a dessert fruit. The storage temperature is 0-1.5°C. The storage period is 30-60 days.

According to the joint online project of the Royal Botanic Gardens at Kew and the Missouri Botanical Garden "The Plant List", the genus has 124 species (for details, see List of species of the genus *Physalis*) [9, 10].

There are several varieties of physalis: garden, strawberry and vegetable. On the basis of Mexican physalis, domestic varieties were obtained, such as Moscow early (early), soil Gribovsky (mid-early), confectionary (mid-late) and large-fruited (mid-late).

Garden physalis is a perennial ornamental plant with bright orange bell-shaped calyxes that is grown as a flower crop.

Physalis garden

Strawberry physalis is an annual fruit group, it can be grown in the middle lane. The fruits of strawberry physalis are amber-colored, sour-sweet, weighing from 7 to 12 g. They are used mainly in the production of compotes and jam.

Physalis alkekengi (*Physalis alkekengi*) — (baboshtan, field cherry, pods, pods, pods, pods, puffballs, core, ball cherry) [11].

A biennial or perennial sparsely pubescent plant of the nightshade family. The stem is erect, up to 60 cm tall, blunt-edged, simple or branched. The leaves are alternate, petiolate, entire, egg-shaped, rounded at the base, pointed at the top. The flowers are bisexual, regular, single, on drooping peduncles, the corolla is wheel-shaped, whitish. Blooms in June - July. The fruit is a rounded orange berry, hidden in a red overgrown cup, ripens in August - September. Grows in forests, among shrubs.

Ripe fruits are harvested. They are used fresh or dried after removing the calyx (the calyx is poisonous). This species is not used for food [12].

Vegetable or Mexican physalis is biologically close to tomatoes, so it is also called Mexican tomato. In terms of biochemical composition, the fruits are not only not inferior to tomatoes, but also superior in some indicators. They have a high pectin content and an optimal ratio of sugar and organic acids. It is an annual plant that can be both short and up to 1 m tall or more. Fruits of vegetable physalis are yellow, green and purple in color, weighing from 30 to 70 g, placed in yellow cups that protect them not only from diseases and pests, but also from low temperatures [13].

The value of the plant is that its fruits contain vitamin C, tannins, caffeic acid, pectin, sugars, carotene.

Physalis fruits are very pleasant to the taste, they are used both raw and processed. In its raw form, it is used in salads, vinaigrettes, soups, and for cooking vegetable caviar. Compotes, jams, jams, marmalade, jelly candies, candies, pie fillings, pickles, mashed potatoes are made from physalis, salted and pickled like tomatoes, sauces, and dried like raisins. Dried physalis has a sweet taste, reminiscent of the taste of raisins, can be used for compotes [14].

It is also very important that physalis fruits have valuable medicinal properties. Ripe fruits without cups are used in food as a dietary product, they are used to prepare confectionery products. Green fruits together with cups are salted and marinated. Red food coloring is obtained from the fruits, which is used to tint butter [15].

The purpose of the work is the development of a technology for the production of functional candies for restaurants by adding physalis fruits to the recipe.

Results.

Physalis is considered an excellent source of carbohydrates, fructose and glucose, the content of the latter can reach 6%. It contains many active substances,

such as polyphenols, tannin, physalin, cryptoxanthin, flavonoids, saponins, citric acid. Physalis fruit can replace multivitamin preparations, it contains vitamins A, B1, B2, B6, B12, minerals magnesium, phosphorus, calcium, sodium, iron, zinc, but most of all potassium.

Berries contain many organic acids: malic, tartaric, citric, amber, caffeic, ferulic and mustard. Physalis contains lycopene, a natural substance that gives the fruits a bright color. Lycopene has a pronounced antioxidant effect and can be used to prevent cancer. Physalis also contains the alkaloid physalin. It is bitter, there is not much of it in the fruits, but because of this, the plant was popularly called the sleepy grass. And also pectin, which removes toxins, decay products, heavy metals, radionuclides and cholesterol from the body.

Nutritional value of physalis per 100 g of product: 6.3 g of fats, 1.9 g of proteins, 11.2 g of carbohydrates, 0.8 g of ash, 85.4 g of water.

The energy value of the product is 53 kcal per 100 g of berries. This is an excellent dietary product that can maximally diversify the menu of people who want to lose weight.

Candy production technology. The incoming raw material must be prepared accordingly. The physalis is separated from the fruit stalk by hand or using branch cutting machines, then it is inspected to remove damaged, dried berries and impurities. Fruits are thoroughly washed with running water on vibrating washing machines or under a shower on sieves.

Apples and apples used in the production of candies are sorted by quality, washed with cold running water in washing machines of various types or manually under a shower on sieves, then cut and puree is prepared from them.

Sugar-sand undergoes cleaning on sieves with a hole diameter of up to 2.5 mm using a magnetic catcher. The hot mixture of fruit and syrup is filtered on mesh filters of various designs to separate the syrup from the berries.

The obtained mass is rubbed to separate the seeds and the skin on an anti-aging machine. The resulting workpiece contains up to 30% residual moisture, a significant part of which is then removed in an infrared dryer. At this stage, it is possible to introduce various additives to obtain different types of candies, in particular, it is possible to add both fruit purees and syrups with spicy and aromatic herbs. The finished candied mass with a residual moisture content of 19-20% is formed by a die in the form of a rectangular bundle measuring 20x30 mm and cut into bars 100 mm long and dried to a final moisture content of 10-12%, followed by sprinkling them with a mixture of viburnum powder, physalis and starch.

Powder from crushed viburnum seeds and physalis can also be used as a sprinkle, which additionally gives the received candies therapeutic and preventive properties.

Fig. 1. Organoleptic assessment of Candy

Organoleptic evaluation of the quality of finished products was carried out in accordance with DSTU 9799-74. The quality of the finished products was evaluated by the tasting committee on a five-point scale. The selection of samples for research was carried out in accordance with DSTU 5904 - "Confectionery products. Acceptance rules, methods of sample selection and preparation".

According to the organoleptic indicators, it was established that functional candies with physalis had excellent taste, aroma and color indicators.

Conclusions. The conducted analytical and experimental studies allow us to draw conclusions that the biological features and main advantages of physalis fruits indicate the possibility of its use in the food industry to obtain functional food products, in particular candies, as well as to be used for therapeutic and preventive purposes. According to the organoleptic indicators, it was established that functional candies with physalis had excellent taste, aroma and color indicators.

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